

An Attempt to Calculate Fractional Charge from QCD

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Abstract

This note is presented with a single aim; the aim is to deduce a mathematical formula to simply calculate the specific quark charge quantum number using higher calculative QCD.

Keywords: QCD, Asymptotic Freedom, Color Confinement

Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) is the quantum field theory with SU(3) gauge group that attempts to understand the strong nuclear force in deeper levels. Quarks [1] are the fundamental fermions that makes up ordinary matter the other being electrons (first generation lepton, a fermion). The necessary of color charge is very crucial in constructing QCD, the two important properties of QCD is 1. Colour confinement and 2. Asymptotic freedom. The gauge field (and consequently eight gauge bosons, gluon) of QCD carry colour charge means apart from mediating the strong force, the strong quanta also participate in self colour interaction. Quarks are never observed in isolated state it is found in composite states called hadrons, this paradox is explained using the discovery called asymptotic freedom [2], it means that the closer the quarks are the weaker the force is between them and as the distance between the quarks grows the force gets stronger and stronger. In other words, for QCD the beta function explains that as the energy scale increases (length scale decreases) the strong coupling gets weaker and as the energy scale

decreases (length scale increases) the coupling or interaction strength gets stronger. Gluon -Gluon self interaction due to color charge constrains a narrow tube or color gauge fields called flux tube or QCD strings, this stretching of gauge fields exerts force thus generating confinement of quarks.

Fig.A explains that gluon field stretches and tension increases which causes color confinement between quarks

The beta function in terms of energy Q and coupling α_s is

$$\beta = \partial \alpha_s / \partial \ln Q$$

The quantum propagator of QCD is gluon of eight types, therefore the Dirac Fermions quarks (especially and only up flavor, charm flavor and top flavor)

Electric charge can be calculated as follows

$$Q = \frac{4}{7} T_R^4 B \left(10 C_A^2 - 3 q_\mu - \frac{1}{2} S_\mu C_{\mu\sigma}^2 \right)$$

$C_{\mu\sigma}$ is the overall gauge fields states means bound gluons

Where $T_R = \frac{1}{2}$ from QCD, B is the baryon number of quarks = 1/3, q_μ is the total number of quarks in nature in

bound or non-isolated state=6, C_A is the color charge parameter in nature=3, S_μ is the ratio of quark to gluon spin = 1/2. The above

equation or formula holds a relationship with quarks of charge $+2/3$ with other QCD

components (including SU(3) gauge group)

References

[1] [1] M. Gell-Mann, Phys. Letters 8, 214 (1964)

[2] Reliable Perturbative Results for Strong Interactions?* H. David Politzer 25th June 1973